

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE REMEDIAL READING PROGRAM ON PUPILS' PERFORMANCE

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Effectiveness of the Remedial Reading Program on Pupils' Performance

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the remedial reading program on the reading comprehension of pupils at Sta. Lucia Elementary School. Specifically, this study aimed to verify the effectiveness of the proposed special remedial teaching program in developing the skills in getting from the context, noting details and making inferences. The pre-test/ posttest Time Series Experimental Design was used in the study. Based on the Phil-IRI pre-test results, there were a total of sixty pupils who were identified frustration level of readers which were taken as the subjects out of 204 Grade Four Pupils of Sta. Lucia Elementary School. Thus, remedial programs were provided to help these pupils compensate for the insufficient learning in previous academic setting. The remedial teaching in reading skills was applied to the special group given the special remedial teaching which was four times a week for fifteen minutes in each session (30 Grade IV pupils) on lessons on getting meaning from the context, noting details and making inferences. On the other hand, another group of 30 Grade IV pupils served as the regular group given the regular remedial teaching which was two times a week for thirty minutes in each session. Based on the study conducted, it showed that the reading performance of the students in the control and experimental group in the pre-test did not differ significantly on getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences. The effectiveness was indicated when the gain scores of both groups taught by program of remedial teaching. However, special group was significantly higher compared the regular group. The Special Remedial Reading Program for Grade four pupils was proven effective in improving the reading comprehension of the children's reading skill in English since there was a very significant difference between the performances of the two groups after the experiment in favor of the experimental group. The computed mean of the experimental group is almost twice as high as compared to the computed mean of the control group. This indicates that those who underwent to the special remedial reading program had better performance than those who were granted with the regular remedial reading program. The Special Remedial Reading Program was an effective strategy because of the development observed by the pupils. It is suggested that elementary teachers must apply this program especially the special remedial reading session to proliferate its effectiveness and teachers be kept abreast in a new mode of teaching that could maximize pupils' participation as well as promote Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) to the elementary pupils. Thus, this could make a great foundation in their formative system.

Keywords: *effectiveness, remedial, reading, program, performance*

Introduction

Teaching and learning are the main concerns of the teacher since learning is the ultimate purpose of teaching. Meaningful learning to all learners will be positively achieved in all aspects of their lives if educators remain alert to the research that is continually providing effective and useful strategies to increase their repertoire of instructional skills.

Youths now days are not that well educated until they become effective readers. Since reading is the primary avenue to all knowledge, it offers access to inform, ideas, aspiration, and happenings of both future and the present. Furthermore, reading can invigorate individuals to be responsible productive members of the society. It is the vehicle of education, the means through which ideas, information, knowledge and wisdom are expressed and exchanged. Literate individuals possess the capacity to function fully in society: to make reasoned choices, to acquire meaningful employment, to participate in civic affairs.

The future success of children lies in the ability to read fluently and understand what they read. Reading is about understanding written texts. It is a complex activity that involves both perception and thought. Reading consists of two related processes: word recognition and comprehension. Word recognition refers to the process of perceiving how written symbols correspond to one's spoken language. Comprehension is the process of making sense of words, sentences and connected texts. Readers typically make use of background knowledge, vocabulary, grammatical knowledge, experience with text and other strategies to help them understand written texts.

Learning to read is an important educational goal. For both children and adults, the ability to read opens up new worlds and opportunities. It enables us to gain new knowledge, enjoy literature, and do everyday things that are part and parcel of modern life, such as, reading the newspapers, job listings, instruction manuals, maps and so on. Most people learn to read in their native language without difficulty. Many, but not all, learn to read as children. Some children and adults need additional help. Reading is one of the academic areas in which one demands success from all children. Unfortunately, everyone knows that success is not always possible. There are many poor readers or even non-readers in the elementary schools. More alarming is the observation that too many of the children leave the school with insufficient competence in this tool for learning.

Because of the obvious importance of success in reading, schools invest enormous sums in initial teaching of reading and remedial

services for struggling readers, two of which are the remedial reading program and the use of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) to assess and evaluate the reading level of the school children. In addition to the importance of providing remedial reading programs to support students' reading skills, it is also important to provide data to indicate that these programs are effective. Because teachers are asked to demonstrate the importance of their programs, providing evidence demonstrating programs are effective is imperative. Providing documentation of an increase in reading comprehension for students participating in reading programs will support continuation of these activities for schools in a time when schools are being asked to provide data about the effectiveness of programs.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of an English remedial teaching on low-achieving students. The goal of remedial teaching is to provide low-achieving students with more chances to reinforce the basic knowledge in common subjects so that they can meet minimum academic standards. Basically, remedial teaching is a type of clinical teaching. It is a "spiral process of assessment—instruction—re-assessment" (Tseng, 2008, p.9). The subjects are targeted at low achievement learners, or under-prepared students. After the teacher diagnoses students' learning difficulties, a remedial course will be designed in accordance with students' needs. And then the teacher takes initiative in offering the instruction, and an evaluation will be conducted during and after the implementation of the remedial teaching to examine the actual effectiveness of the course. Minor adjustments would be made based on the results of the evaluation to ensure that students are able to catch up in regular classes.

The remedial teaching program of a school plays an important role in the improvement of the educational output thus giving teachers the great responsibility of carrying out a rigid remedial teaching program (Regional Bulletin No. 4, s. 1987). The purpose is to overcome weaknesses discovered in any aspect of the teaching process. It is given to the pupils who are reading below their potential capacities. To strengthen the implementation of this Regional Bulletin No. 4, s. 1987, Schools Division Superintendent issued a division memorandum stating the utilization of break time to conduct Remedial Teaching Program. All Elementary Grade teachers in the public schools must render thirty minutes remedial teaching to all pupils who cannot cope with the lessons and have difficulty in reading. Problems made by pupils can be remedied if and when remedial teaching is properly implemented. In line with this, the researcher proposed a new and shorter schedule conducting remedial teaching. Instead of thirty minutes of remediation during class hours it lessens fifteen minutes. The new schedule for the low-achieving pupils in remedial teaching is fifteen minutes which is done four times a week. The other fifteen minutes in regular class hours is used to make a daily interaction between teacher and pupil. Through this, the remaining fifteen minutes for the actual schedule in remedial teaching may classify as other related activities.

In response to the identified need of enhancing the quality reading skills of the young learners, the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was launched for the past eight (8) years (2004-2012) and currently intensive implementation in the elementary school is being conducted. The program was an initiative of the Bureau of Elementary Education, Department of Education which directly addresses its thrust to make every Filipino Child A Reader Program, "the goal of which is to enable every Filipino child to communicate both English and Filipino through effective remedial reading. Based on the schedule of the conduct of the remedial teaching in school, it was evident that the pupils are getting tired on the activities and lecture method to review the recent lessons. Thirty minutes of remedial teaching is a big factor to the pupils who are still in remedial period.

But then, it is frustrating to know that even with the use of the best strategies, instructional materials and wide exposure of the new technologies, still there are many pupils in the elementary level who cannot read well and cannot comprehend what they read. With this, the researcher proposed a new schedule for remedial teaching to the Grade IV pupils is such an adjustment to them. With appropriate teaching strategies and teachers' competence used as tool in English would greatly contribute to the achievement of the pupils. The best way for students to learn and comprehend on what they read is to experience problems that challenge English, and the thought, habits of mind and actions associated with trying to solve them. Pupils under Remedial Teaching Program have or more than one of the following learning difficulties; poor memory, short attention span and are easily distracted by other things, relatively poor comprehensive power, lack of learning motivation and lack of self-confidence, relatively low self-expectation and fail to transfer knowledge to the related learning area appropriately. Apart from various learning difficulties, pupils may have different abilities and styles of learning. Some are better in visual learning while others are more competent in audio learning. Certain pupils have to learn through sense of touch or practical experiences. Remedial teachers, therefore, should design diversified teaching activities and adopt various teaching methods to help the students develop their potential and remove the obstacles in learning.

As of this time, there has been no assessment on Remedial Teaching Program using the new schedule of fifteen minutes four times a week. Since the researcher is an English teacher of Sta. Lucia Elementary School, Capas West District, Capas, Tarlac and being involved in the remedial teaching, the researcher prompted to undertake this study to find out if the program is being effectively done or not, and thus, further evaluate the effectiveness of the said program.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to find out the effectiveness of the remedial reading program on the reading comprehension of Grade IV pupils at Sta. Lucia Elementary School. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How is the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the pre-test described?
2. How is the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test described?

3. Is there a significant difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group based on the pre-test?
4. Is there a significant difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group based on the post-test?
5. Is there a significant difference between the gained mean of the control and experimental group?
6. What reading enhancement program could be proposed based from the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, subjects of the study, procedure, instrument, and statistical treatment to get the pertinent data in the study.

Research Design

The pre-test/posttest experimental design was used in this study to determine the effectiveness of the Remedial Reading Program, which had two groups of thirty pupils in each group. One group was exposed to regular remedial teaching- twice a week for 30 minutes in each exposure. The other group was exposed to special remedial teaching- four times a week for 15 minutes in each exposure. This study also described the two sessions in remedial teaching program in terms of the different schedule for both groups. It further described the reading and comprehension performance of the Grade Four pupils through the result in the pre-test and posttest. Correlation method was also used to determine the difference between the pre-test and post-test of the two groups.

Participants

Based on the Phil-IRI pre-test results, there were a total of sixty pupils who were identified frustration level of readers which were taken as the subjects out of 204 Grade Four Pupils of Sta. Lucia Elementary School. Thus, remedial programs were provided to help these pupils compensate for the insufficient learning in previous academic setting. The remedial teaching in reading skills was applied to the special group given the special remedial teaching which was four times a week for fifteen minutes in each session (30 Grade IV pupils) on lessons on getting meaning from the context, noting details and making inferences. On the other hand, another group of 30 Grade IV pupils served as the regular group given the regular remedial teaching which was two times a week for thirty minutes in each session.

Instruments

The researcher asked permission to adapt a comprehension test from previous studies conducted about remedial reading. Since the study aimed to determine the effectiveness of remedial teaching in reading skills in getting meaning from the context, noting details and making inferences, the researcher test questions are based on these three reading skills consists of ten items each skill.

This test was administered twice: the first was the pre-test and the second post- test. Based on the three selected reading skills, which the test intended to measure, the test was divided into three reading skills of ten items each. The distribution is indicated as follows:

<i>Reading Skills</i>	<i>Number of Items</i>
Getting Meaning from the Context	10
Noting Details	10
Making Inferences	10

The experiment was done for the duration of 11 weeks. After the 11th week of exposure, the post test was administered to both groups in order to determine the effectiveness of the different frequencies of remedial teaching.

Procedure

In gathering the data needed for this study, the researcher first sought the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor and School Principal of Sta. Lucia Elementary School to distribute the questionnaires through a letter of request. After the approval of the permit, the researcher reproduced enough copies of the questionnaire and personally did the distribution and retrieval so instructions were explained thoroughly to the respondents. Then, both special and regular remedial teachings were implemented to see how effective remedial teaching was to frustration readers. (See Appendix for the Instructional Plans).

The two groups were given a pre-test. Then the same lessons, materials and references were taught to the classes. The teaching sessions were carefully scheduled so that the both groups were exposed to the same period conditions. The actual teaching was done for eleven weeks with a total of 50 days conduct of the study was implemented last June 03 – August 14, 2015.

The following schedules were followed throughout the experiment.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Days</i>	<i>Group of Pupils</i>
11:30 – 11:45 am	Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, and Thursday	Special
4:00-4:30 pm	Wednesday and Friday	Regular

A pre-test was administered to the special group and regular group before the experimentation. The pre-test results were compared to find if the level of performance of the special group and regular group were the same.

The pre-test and post-test results of the two groups were analyzed statistically to determine the effectiveness of the Remedial Teaching. The post test results of the two groups were compared to determine which group performed better.

The following were done in conducting the special remedial reading program.

During Mondays, pupils read a passage (short paragraph, story, poems, and dialogues) on the skills to be taught individually, by two's or in groups. During Tuesdays, the teacher asked questions orally to the pupils after reading the selection. Answers were located in the passage. During Wednesdays, the teacher gave another passage for the pupils to read to reinforce the skill being taught. During Thursday, a written quiz was given by the teacher to check the skill learned by the pupils. The teacher got the mastery level by frequency and if $\frac{1}{2}$ of the pupils failed to get 4 items correctly, they have to repeat the lesson.

The following steps were done in conducting the regular remedial reading program.

During Wednesdays, reading of a passage (short paragraph, story, dialogue) and asking questions and answering were done by the pupils orally. During Fridays, reading of another passage by the pupils and giving a written quiz. Getting the mastery level of teaching and if $\frac{1}{2}$ of the pupils failed to get 4 items correctly, they have to repeat the lesson. After the instruction was made the collection and the results were tabulated.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered from the study. The answers to the questions posed in the study are shown per problem.

Reading performance of the control and experimental group in the pre-test

This study was focused on determining the effectiveness of the remedial reading program on the reading comprehension of the grade four pupils at Sta. Lucia Elementary School. In the application of the program, thirty (30) pupils classified as frustration readers belonged to the regular and special group. These groups were given a pre-test and post-test with 10 items each skill and a total number of 30 items. The skills tested were as follows: getting the meaning from context, noting details and making inferences. These areas hopefully captured the status of the reading comprehension skills of the pupils which would serve as a basis in designing appropriate reading enhancement program.

Vocabulary is an important tool for communication. A person can communicate well the message he wants to put across when he has a wide and rich store of vocabulary. A word may have several meanings or definitions. However, the exact meaning of the word could be inferred on how the word is used in the sentence and by looking at the word and sentences around it. This is appropriately done by getting the meaning through context. In this area, students were asked to get meaning of the underlined word through context. The ability or skills to recognize which ideas are important to remember and be read with care is noting details. Students' ability to note details shows the sharpness of their minds in noticing oddness in information or facts presented.

Inference is drawing conclusions based on information that has been implied rather than directly stated and is an essential skill in reading comprehension. Making inferences requires students to combine what they are reading with what they already know, to reach into their own personal knowledge and apply it to what they are reading.

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the pre-test scores of the Grade IV pupils in the three comprehension skills which is getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences.

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Pretest Scores*

Control Group			
Scores	Frequency (f)	Percentage(P)	Mean
1-5	6	20	8.3
6-10	17	53	
11-15	9	27	
Total	30	100	
Experimental Group			
1-5	2	7	8.93
6-10	20	67	
11-15	8	26	
Total	30	100	

The table above gives an overall picture about the pupils' performance in their pre-test before the remedial reading program was introduced to each group. Based on the result, it is obvious that the respondents are weak in the three comprehension skills as indicated in the results of all the said areas. As the data presented above, the control group got a mean of 8.3 and the experimental group obtained 8.93 mean.

Table 1 shows the result of the respondents' performance the three comprehension skills which is getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences. The control group got a mean of scores of 8.3 in the pre-test. This reflected in the table where 6 or

20.00% of the respondents whose score range from 1-5, added to it is the slightly effective performance of 17 or

53.00 % of the respondents who obtained a score of 6-10 in a 30 item test. The table also shows that only 9 or 27.00 % got a score from 11-15.

As shown in the table, the statistical result on the three content area, the experimental group obtained a mean of 8.93. This indicates the weakness or difficulty of pupils in the three comprehension skills tested. Only 2 or 7% obtained a score of 1-5 which only shows that few students have an effective performance in terms of context clues, noting details and making inferences. What also frustrating is that, 20 out of 30 of the respondents or 67.00% under the score 6-10 and which indicates a not effective performance along the three areas. The pupils' performance shows that 8 or 26% among 30 respondents whose scores range from 11-15. Result showed that pupils have low scores, which meant that they have no prior knowledge of the subject matter.

The pupils showed a poor stock knowledge of vocabularies in terms of getting meaning from context and that only few have a wide vocabulary as accounted in the result. Since this skill is very essential in comprehending the reading text, it is therefore advice that teachers must look for means on how to improve the students' performance in figuring out the meaning to words presented. It points also to a serious problem that a number of students lack the needed skill in locating even surface data in a reading text. This indicates that actions must be done by the teachers to uplift students' performance in terms of noting details. This means that there is a need to conduct remediation to the students in order to uplift their performance not only on comprehension as in reading the lines but also in between and beyond the lines and be able to figure out information which is not directly stated or explained in the text. The results of the pre-test and the information gathered motivated the researcher to conduct a remediation program that would help the pupils particularly the non-readers to read and the teacher to make reading lesson an easy task.

Reading performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test

The reading comprehension of the respondents was assessed through the use of pre-test and post-test. These served as a very valuable source of assessment information for teachers and students' themselves. After the pre-test, the experimentation was conducted on the selected reading skills in getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences.

Part of reading comprehension involves using the other words in a sentence or passage to understand an unknown word. An author often includes hints, or clues, to help the reader expand vocabulary and grasp the meaning of the passage. Skill in using context clues enables a reader to comprehend advance texts.

The ability or skills to recognize which ideas are important to remember and be read with care is noting details. Students' ability to note details shows the sharpness of their minds in noticing oddness in information or facts presented.

Readers who make inferences use the clues in the text along with their own experiences to help them figure out what is not directly said, making the text personal and memorable. Helping students make texts memorable will help them gain more personal pleasure from reading, read the text more critically, and remember and apply what they have read.

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the post-test scores Grade IV pupils' in the three comprehension skills which is getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of Post-test Scores*

Control Group			
<i>Scores</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage(P)</i>	<i>Mean</i>
6-10	2	7	
11-15	14	47	
16-20	13	43	15.16
21-25	1	3	
Total	30	100	
Experimental Group			
11-15	5	17	
16-20	15	50	
21-25	9	30	19.06
25-30	1	3	
Total	30	100	

Table 2 displays the reading performance of the control group and experimental group in the post-test. Focusing on the outcome of the post-test of the two groups, both have improved their reading skills. As the data presented above, the control group got a grand mean of 15.16 and the experimental group obtained 19.06 grand mean.

As shown in table 2, it could be noted that the pupils in control and experimental group registered an improvement scores in the posttest. As seen in the table, all reading skills greatly improved and gained high scores. In the performances of the pupils of the control group in in the pre-test were the result was slightly effective or 8.3 mean, it could be noted that the performances of the pupils in the post-test scored better by implementing the program of remedial teaching it was found effective with a mean of 15.16. All reading skills greatly

improved after the experimentation of the program.

A close examination of the results that reveals that there was an increased with the scores of the pupils of the experimental group in the post-test, from 8.93 of mean it went dramatically to

19.16. The pupils were able to identify and recognize the meaning of the word and took advantage of context clues given, through this; the pupils were able to easily define difficult or unusual words. The pupils' performance in noting details shows also a great improvement of mean in the posttest. It could be noted that the pupils have the courage to classify from a piece of text the piece or pieces of information to achieve a given purpose such as answering a question in a text. Likewise, in making inferences the pupils' increased their ability to use what they know and how to make a guess about and what they do not know or reading between the lines in the posttest.

This further shows that majority of the pupil respondents were applying the concept of remediation and this indicated that using strategy greatly affected the performance of the pupils due to exposure to the procedure and elaboration of concepts.

As shown in the table, the statistical result on three content areas in the post-test, a mean of 15.16 showed that regular remedial teaching to control group is effective. This indicates that the respondents have improved in the three content areas that would mean better performance in their comprehension skill. None of the students got a score of 0-5 and that 2 or 7% obtained a score of 6-10 which only shows that few students have a slightly effective performance in the post-test. It is also interesting to note that out of 30 students who took the 30-item test, 14 (47%) got a score of 11-15, 13(43%) got a scored 16-20, and 1 (3%) got a score 21-25.

As shown in table 2, 5 respondents of the experimental group obtained a score of 11-15 comprised 17%, 15 respondents got a score of 16-20 comprising of 50% each students. There were 9 pupils or 30% got a score of 21-25, 1 pupil also or 3% got a score range from 21-25, no respondents obtained a score of 0 to 10. The mean of scores of 19.06 obtained by the respondents revealed an effective performance in the post-test of the experimental group.

Based from the result of the test, majority of the students have greatly improved in getting meaning from context. The students are now able to figure out the definition, phrases and words that help them to make a guess about the word's meaning. The students have greatly improved also in noting details. The students are now able to recognize which ideas are important to remember and be read with care in a passage or selection. This means that through remediation conducted to the students, teachers have uplift their performance not only on comprehension as in reading the lines but also in between and beyond the lines and they were able to figure out information which is not directly stated or explained in the text. This indicates that the respondents have improved in three content areas that would mean better performance in their comprehension skill.

This result indicates that pupils who were taught using remedial lessons in reading performed higher and better in reading comprehension test. Higher progress could be observed in the reading performance of the pupils to whom remediation was introduced. With these gathered data, it was observed that there was a very significant difference between the mean of the two groups compared to their pre-test scores, wherein the experimental group who are exposed to the special remedial reading program earns higher score than the control group who are exposed to the regular remedial reading program.

Difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group based on the pre-test

Table 3 presents the result of the experiment to test the effectiveness of the remedial reading program to the grade four pupils. A pre-test was provided to the subjects before the experimental period, and then a post-test was handed to the same subjects after the instruction. The table shows the statistical difference of the two groups between their pre-test performances.

Table 3. *Difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the pre-test*

<i>Degree of freedom</i>	<i>Alpha Level</i>	<i>Anova Value</i>	<i>Critical value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Result</i>
58	.05	5.400	.418	Accept the null hypothesis	There is no significant difference between the Scores in Pre-test of Control and Experimental Group

Table 3 shows that there is no significant difference between the pretest score of control and experimental group. With the $p=.418$ falls beyond $CI= \alpha .05$ therefore the null hypothesis was accepted. This result indicates that the reading performance of the students in the control and experimental group in the pre-test did not differ significantly on getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences.

Difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test

The difference of the performances of the pupils before the program had been used would show the effectiveness of the program both in the special and regular group. The effectiveness was indicated when the gain scores of the both groups taught by program of remedial teaching special group was significantly higher than the regular group.

Table 4. *Difference between the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test*

Degree of freedom	Alpha Level	ANCOVA VALUE	Critical value	Decision	Result
58	.05	24.039	.000	Reject the null hypothesis	There is a significant difference between the Scores in post-test of Control and Experimental Group

Findings in table 4 revealed that the reading performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test differed significantly since the $p=.000$ falls within $CI= \alpha .05$ therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. It was clearly evaluated that the performance of the pupils improved. This means that the remedial teaching was effective considering the scores of the pupils improved, but as seen in the table, the special group registered higher scores than the pupils in the regular group. This showed that the schedule in special remedial teaching (four times a week for 15 minutes in each exposure) was more effective in teaching than to regular remedial teaching (twice a week for 30 minutes in each exposure). The change in the mean on the regular group was observed, this means that the regular remedial teaching is also effective.

Difference between the gain mean of the control and experimental group

Table 5. *Difference between the Gain Mean of the Experimental and Control Group*

	Pre-Test Mean	Post-Test Mean	Gain Mean
Control	8.3	15.16	6.86
Experimental	8.93	19.06	10.13

Table 5 illustrates the difference between the gain mean of the experimental and control group. It shows that the control group gained a mean of 6.86, whereas the experimental group garnered a gain mean of 10.13. The data confirmed that the experimental and control group similarly have improved in their reading performances which both were very significant. Based on the given figures, a great change could be observed on the reading performance of the pupils, wherein the conclusion favored the use of the special remedial reading program than that of the regular remedial reading program.

This is a strategy in remedial teaching program in teaching English that deals with short period of time in teaching different concepts to the pupils prior to the schedule given by the teachers during the class.

In application of the new schedule, pupils work by the assistance of the teacher to discuss the lessons presented to them. After the given time, the class will be given activities wherein topics about reading skills were the subject matter. The comparison of the performances of the students before the strategy had been used would show the effectiveness of the strategy during the pre-test and posttest. The effectiveness was indicated when the gain scores of the group taught by concept of special remedial teaching was significantly effective than the regular remedial teaching.

The results of the testing shows gain scores in the post-test performance from the pre-test of the group. A close examination of the results that reveals that there was an increased with the scores of the pupils of the control group from 8.3 of mean it went dramatically to 15.16. Likewise, the pupils' of the experimental group shows also a great improvement from 8.93 mean in the pre-test it went dramatically to 19.06 mean in the post-test. This means that after the learning topics on reading skills using remedial teaching program, the control and experimental group greatly improved in the posttest. This further shows that majority of the pupil respondents were applying the concept of remediation and this indicated that using strategy greatly affected the performance of the pupils due to exposure to the procedure and elaboration of concepts.

The pupils who are part of the Experimental (treatment Group) receive a higher score in the post test. As evidence, the comparison between the results of the post-test of the experimental and control groups, both have improved their reading skills. However, higher progress could be observed in the reading performance of the pupils to whom the Special Remedial Reading Program was introduced.

The study's goal of enhancing the reading skill of the grade four pupils through the special remedial reading program was achieved. The attainment of the children in reading measures the success of the teaching-learning process. With the belief that reading is an important skill an individual has to learn, the special remedial reading program became a basis in creating reading enhancement program that could make a big difference to those pupils who often are unable to read words by their level. Implementing the Special Remedial Reading Program is another effective technique in reading that will help a non-reader child learns the skill better. Correct implementation and honest remediation practices with proper guidance and attention from teachers and parents will make a child quickly learn to read.

Reading Enhancement Program

Based on the analysis of the data, a reading enhancement program is needed to address the present reading comprehension performance of the Grade IV pupils of Sta. Lucia Elementary School. The school should pay attention to the need to improve the reading comprehension performance of the pupils.

This program is expected to serve as the instrument for the delivery of a high quality instruction not only for the Grade IV pupils but

also for the other grade level pupils. Following is the proposed Reading Enhancement Program.

This reading program proposed to improve and enhance the reading performance of Grade IV pupils of Sta. Lucia Elementary School. As reflected in the program, the students are provided with activities and strategies to reinforce these essential vocabulary and reading comprehension skills.

Table 6. *Reading Enhancement Program*

<i>Areas of Concerns</i>	<i>Strategies</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Means of Verification</i>
To determine the reading levels of pupils.	Phil-IRI	Reading Assessment (PHIL-IRI Pre-test) Requiring pupils to have reading portfolio. To monitor their reading profile.	Report of Reading results, Portfolio and Phil-IRI
Trim down number of pupils who are under "Frustration" level in reading.	Remedial reading session can be done. Reward system will motivate them to participate.	Conduct daily remedial classes with focus on least learned skills. Read-a-Paragraph- A-Day (APAD)	Report of Phil-IRI
To develop among pupils the habit and love for reading	Audio Assisted Reading Rhyming Games	Read-One-Word-A- Day (ROWD) Spell-Pronounce- Read-Write (SPRITE) Project DEAR (Drop Everything and Read)	Pupils Reading Portfolio
To develop parents' involvement in reading of the pupils.	Conference with the parents for their child's reading performance. Reflecting on challenges to the pupil's belief in values	Parents' Assistance for Reading Excellence (PARE)	Reading Remedial Logbook Signed by the Parents.
To give recognition to best performing pupils.	Reading Contest	Camp to Conduct Story Telling and Retelling Jazz Chants	Report in Reading Results

Implication of findings to Educational Leadership

The implications were based from the result of this study, the effectiveness of remedial reading program wherein the reading comprehension of the two groups of respondents were analyzed and compared. The result revealed that special remedial reading program is effective. Therefore, educators should employ this program in teaching English Reading.

Reading is the construction of meaning from text through background interest, attitude, purpose and ability (Jennings, et al., 2006). These are the five areas essential for success in reading. Literacy is an integral part of the society- providing opportunities in education, employment, social adjustment, and entertainment (McCormick, 2007). Throughout many years of research, discussions, and theories it has been most advantageous to discover some of the latest enhancement reading programs that would help both the teachers and students as regard to learning.

The results of the study certainly revealed the real scenario that characterizes students in terms of the performance in reading comprehension. We have faced the fact that some students now have poor reading comprehension. Teachers should be vigilant enough in doing their roles, so the students as well as the educational system will not be left behind by other developing countries as shown in several studies and observations including their work.

This study was concerned with determining the "Effectiveness of the Remedial Reading Program on the Reading Comprehension of Grade IV Pupils at Sta. Lucia Elementary School". To begin with, there should be focus on the findings that revealed pupils reading performance in the pre-test of the regular and special group. It is important to note that pupils who were neglected to remedial classes experienced difficulty in understanding the text. The pupils in the regular and special group obtained low scores in the pre-test, it only shows that they have poor reading performance in English and so teachers must still improve in teaching the students to read with comprehension. On the other hand, it is interesting to note that pupils exposed to remedial classes both in regular and special group gained improvement in their post-test scores. Therefore, both regular and special remedial reading program are both effective in improving the reading performance of the pupils.

The findings will serve as a basis for designing lessons that the Remedial classes will have. It is suggested that teachers should implement the Special Remedial Reading Program to cater the needs of the learners and to improve their reading comprehension skills. This can also serve as a guide for the remedial reading teachers in preparing activities that students can enjoy while reading.

The government should therefore support more reading programs in the Philippines and encourage administrators and teachers design programs that will address the needs of the students when it comes to reading. Lack of ability in oral reading means lack of confidence to communicate with other people. If Filipinos cannot have the confidence, it is impossible for us to be productive individuals and globally competitive citizens.

A total transformation should be accomplished. Actions should be taken on this matter to at most strengthen the students' performance in reading comprehension. High performance could be attained if it would be worked out by all concerned authorities.

Conclusion

Based on the results and findings, the following conclusions are drawn: (1) In terms of the reading performance of the control group and experimental group in the pre-test, who are exposed to regular and special remedial reading program registered a verbal description of slightly effective. (2) The reading performance of the respondents of the control group in the post-test who are exposed to regular remedial reading program was interpreted as moderately effective. On the other hand, the respondents of the experimental group in the post-test who are exposed to the special remedial reading program obtained effective reading performance. Due to this result, it can be deduced that both remediation program as a strategy in teaching has an effect to the students in understanding literary text. (3) The reading performance of the students in the control and experimental group in the pre-test did not differ significantly on getting meaning from context, noting details and making inferences. The effectiveness was indicated when the gain scores of the both groups taught by program of remedial teaching. However, special group was significantly higher compared the regular group. (4) The Special Remedial Reading Program for Grade four pupils was proven effective in improving the reading comprehension the children's reading skill in English since there was a very significant difference between the performances of the two groups after the experiment in favor of the experimental group. The computed mean of the experimental group is almost twice as high as compared to the computed mean of the control group. This indicates that those who underwent to the special remedial reading program had better performance than those who were granted with the regular remedial reading program. The Special Remedial Reading Program was an effective strategy because of the development observed by the pupils. (5) The enhancement program developed in the study included strategies to address the weaknesses of the students in reading in all levels of comprehension which teachers could adopt in conducting remedial reading classes. (6) Remedial Teaching Program can be repetitive process, which can be frustrating for both the student and the teacher. Luckily, there are many resources such as remedial reading activities out that are both effective and provide variety.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested: (1) Teachers must effectively diagnose the causes of the difficulties or weaknesses of the students in reading along all the levels of comprehension. This could be done by giving pre-test before the instruction. In this way, teachers could use appropriate strategies. Teachers must not discount the possibility of the occurrence of reading disabilities since students are already in the intermediate grade. It is expected that at this stage, they should have already acquired high reading competence. Teachers should administer pre-test and posttest to the pupils, to find out where the students are and whether or not the pupils' performances improve. (2) It is suggested that the Regular Remedial Teaching Program and Special Remedial Teaching program should be properly implemented. Specifically, the topics on vocabulary development, comprehension skills and using the dictionary. It should be implemented as well depending on the preferred schedule of the pupils. (3) It is suggested that elementary teachers must apply this program especially the special remedial teaching session to proliferate its effectiveness and teachers be kept abreast in a new mode of teaching that could maximize pupils' participation as well as promote Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) to the elementary pupils. Thus, this could make a great foundation in their formative system. (4) Teachers should also teach students study skills to help them become motivated, independent and responsible for their own learning. These skills will be invaluable throughout their school life. (5) Parents should not leave to the teacher the tasks alone; they should be concerned with their children's performance in reading. Teachers should let the parents be involved in planning the remedial teaching to get their full cooperation and support. (6) The enhancement program could be adopted by teachers to improve the reading performance of the students in remedial reading classes. (7) Further study should be done using the special remedial teaching especially in the intermediate level.

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